

ROLE OF TECHNOLOGY IN TIMES OF COVID-19 PANDEMIC: A BOON**Krishna Kulin Trivedi***M.Com (Gold Medalist) Research Scholar, School Of Commerce, Gujarat University***Abstract:-**

The whole world fights against the corona virus disease which is an infectious respiratory disease also known as COVID-19 which has been declared as a pandemic by the World Health Organization popularly known in short as WHO. Because of the massive spread of the disease and to control and stop the spread of the disease complete lockdown and curfew was implemented to control and stop the spread of this disease. And thus in this hard times of COVID-19 Pandemic, technology proved a boon to us in carrying out ICT enabled learning, E-Banking, E-Business, E-Payments, E-Commerce, Work from home, ICT enabled Entertainment, various applications which helps tracing the spread of this infectious communicable respiratory disease, share market, contactless delivery in this hard times to control the spread of infection and avoid going out, robotics for various services, applications for staying fit at home, learning cooking, education, to monitor the temperatures with the help of wireless thermometers etc. thus, in this hard and difficult times of pandemic technology proved a boon.

Keywords: Technology, ICT, COVID-19, Pandemic, Digital Transformation, the New Normal, India, Boon

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Introduction

Health is Wealth, in our nation India our prime minister rightly said JAAN HAI TO JAHAN HAI which means if you have life, you have the world thus our prime minister thought about ourselves and our lives and imposed complete lockdown in our nation India to control and stop the spread of this newly discovered virus. In this hard times where the whole world fights with this pandemic situation, it will affect the whole economy, increase unemployment, financial crises, reverse migration in the rural areas, increase poverty, reduce the standard of living, increase the cost of living etc. The whole world fights against the corona virus disease which is an infectious respiratory disease also known as COVID-19 which has been declared as a pandemic by the World Health Organization popularly known in short as WHO. Because of the massive spread of the disease and to control and stop the spread of the disease complete lockdown and curfew was implemented to control and stop the spread of this disease. And thus in this hard times of COVID-19 Pandemic, technology proved a boon to us in carrying out ICT enabled learning, E-Banking, E-Business, E-Payments, E-Commerce, Work from home, online Entertainment, applications tracing the spread of this infectious communicable respiratory disease, share market, contactless delivery in this hard times to control the spread of infection and avoid going out, robotics for various services, applications for staying fit at home, learning cooking, education, to monitor the temperatures with the help of wireless thermometers etc. thus, in this hard and difficult times of pandemic technology proved a boon.

In this hard times of COVID-19 pandemic it is the technology which keeps us together, help trace the spread of infections, helps to communicate across the globe, online learning for the millions of students to continue with their studies and in continuance with their academic calendar so that their academic is not affected, contactless delivery, ICT enabled learning, E-Banking, E-Business, E-Payments, E-Commerce, Work from home a flexible solution, online Entertainment via various digital platforms, applications developed specially for tracing the spread of this infectious communicable respiratory disease, share market, contactless delivery in this hard times to control the spread of infection and avoid going out, robotics for various services, applications for staying fit at home, learning cooking, education, to monitor the temperatures with the help of wireless thermometers etc. thus, in this hard and difficult times of pandemic technology proved a boon and helped us in this hard times of pandemic situation to survive in this situation.

Review of Literature

Mihalis Kritikos, 2020 of the Scientific Foresight Unit (STOA) studied in depth how the distinct 10 technological domains are serving to fight against the communicable COVID-19 Disease which has been declared as pandemic by the World Health Organization (WHO) by ways of innovative new, useful applications. It enlightens and focus on the greater legal and regulatory disputes and on the key socio-ethical difficult for the varied utilisation of those technologies pose when applied in a very public-health emergency context like the communicable Covid-19 pandemic disease.

Veena Shenoy, Sheetal Mahendher, 2020 have studied that due to the adoption and the global trend of digitalisation and technology in higher education it has created the uprising of it. In Bangalore rather than the regular traditional classroom teaching most of the higher education has widely adopted the technology and students involvement towards it.

Daniel, 2020 gave a determination to the issue for coexisting method of learning.

The research finished by him reveal a productive response as this method is quite simple and easy for remote The UK Open University who had already started using this technique during the COVID19 pandemic. Educational Institutes, Academic Fraternity, and students Group should follow to use more flexible, new and innovative methods to retrieve the damage and loss done by the communicable COVID-19 Pandemic Disease.

Objective of the Study

The research paper has the following subsequent objectives:

- To know and understand about the role of technology which is a boon to us in this difficult and hard times of COVID-19 Pandemic.
- To know in which areas technology helped us to move forward with this ongoing situation and helped us to survive in this Pandemic situation.
- To draw a conclusion.

Scope of the Research Study

The present research study has been undertaken to know about digitalisation trend, and also the role of technology which could be a boon to us during this difficult and adversity of COVID-19 Pandemic, to understand during which areas technology helped us to move forward with this ongoing situation and helped us to survive during this Pandemic situation. this research study are going to be of immense help to the tutorial circle, research scholar group, policy makers, students, corporates, researchers and organizations to attain an insight about the role of technology which is that the most vital a part of our life and therefore the new normal and a boon during this adversity of Covid-19

Pandemic. With the help of this present research study, further changes and development for a much better smarter future with the assistance of technology are often made by knowing this scenario of the present situation and may be helpful for future planning and framing strategies for a successful mission and for better development. The study relies on the foremost important and ongoing topic i.e. role of technology in times of covid-19 pandemic: a boon and with this research study advancement further in technology are often planned, steps to develop it further and planning and strategy formulation will be made for the long term.

Research Methodology

The Word “Research” Is Split In Two Parts “RE” And “SEARCH “Which Means To Look Again And Again. It's A Scientific Thanks To Carry A Study On A Selected Topic. The Term Research Methodology Is That The Procedure Won't To Find, Choose, Filter And Analyse Information A Couple Of Particular Topic. To Fulfil The Above-Mentioned Objective, Secondary Data Is Employed. This Research Work Could Be A Blend Of Descriptive And Exploratory Research Work And Has Extensively Used The Secondary Data Method For The Research Study. The Research Study Undertaken Is Solely Secondary. The Knowledge Employed In This Study Is Collected Through Various Newspaper, Magazines, Conference Proceedings, Websites, Journals, And Books Etc To Gather Various Data For The Data Collected Employed In This Study.

Role of Technology in Times of Covid-19 Pandemic: A Boon

In this hard difficult and times with full crises and COVID-19 Pandemic, the innovations in technology proved a boon to us in carrying out ICT enabled learning, Electronic Banking, Digital Business, Electronic Payments also knowns as Cashless Payments, Electronic Commerce the global trend, Work from home a flexible solution, online Entertainment via various digital platforms, applications developed specially for tracing the spread of this infectious communicable respiratory disease, share market, contactless delivery in this hard times to control the spread of infection and avoid going out, robotics for various services, applications for staying fit at home, learning cooking, education, to monitor the temperatures with the help of wireless thermometers etc. thus, in this hard and difficult times of pandemic technology proved a boon. With technology it assisted us in managing the things very effectively and efficiently. In this hard times where the whole world fights with this pandemic situation, it will affect the whole economy, increase unemployment, financial crises, reverse migration in the rural areas, increase poverty, reduce the standard of living, increase the cost of living etc. In this hard and difficult times of pandemic technology proved a boon, below mentioned are few of the activities and services with the help of technology in this difficult and hard times of COVID-19 Pandemic:

- **Information And Communications Technology Enabled Learning**

In this hard and difficult times of COVID-19 Pandemic, the schools and colleges were shut down and in such situation to continue with the learning and with the academic calendar the ICT enabled learning proved a boon for millions of students across the globe. Online learning which also known as Digital learning is, ICT enabled learning, E-learning is learning with the use of electronic device and electronic learning. The online learning has gained a significant increase in demand and is widely accepted. The online learning which is a boon in this hard times of pandemic is widely accepted and in future online learning along with traditional learning also known as Blended Learning can be planned off.

- **Entertainment Via Online Platforms**

The whole world fights against the corona virus disease which is an infectious respiratory disease also knowns as

COVID-19 which has been declared as a pandemic by the World Health Organization popularly known in short as WHO. Because of the massive spread of the disease and to control and stop the spread of the disease complete lockdown and curfew was implemented to control and stop the spread of this disease. thus, in this times online streaming of live shows, music concerts, various applications like YOUTUBE, HOTSTAR, Amazon Prime, NETFLIX, various gaming applications proved a boon to entertain the people and keep them fit, health, fresh in this hard times of Pandemic situation.

- **Applications Tracing The Spread Of Covid-19 Infection**

The applications specially developed for health for tracing the spread of disease, knowing the red, orange and green zones, knowing the number of cases with the Aarogya Setu application build in our nation India helped the whole nation in tracing the spread of COVID-19 infection in the nation India. By this we can know where how much spread is there of the disease and know the Red zone where the number of spread of infection is high. Even the telecom partners used the caller tunes for spreading the awareness of this disease and take the protective measures like to wear face mask, wash hands frequently with soaps/sanitizer, maintain social and physical distancing, avoid touching of eyes nose and mouth.

- **Stock Market**

The digitalisation trend and adoption of technology in share market increased the trading volumes in this pandemic situation and helped the stake holders, investors, clients to access the market situation by staying at home and spend their time in stock market.

- **Contactless Deliveries**

In this hard times of Pandemic situation, lockdown situation there came a significant increase and high demand to online grocery market and contactless delivery. With the help of various applications like Big Basket, Zomato, Swiggy people avoided going out standing in long ques and preferred contactless deliveries. Vegetables, Fruits, Milk, Food packets etc. were delivered with online orders.

- **Robotics**

The Covid-19 Pandemic has made us realize the importance of Robots. The Robots can be used to serve in hospitals to the infected persons, to clean the infected area, to deliver foods to quarantine people etc. Even drones were used to deliver food, food packets, medicines, transportation test kits etc.

- **Various Beneficial Applications**

In this hard, strange and difficult times with full of financial crises and COVID-19 Pandemic disease, various applications for entertainment fun and enjoyment, education-learning, cookery shows, fitness and health applications etc. proved useful for the people staying indoors to keep them fit, fresh and healthy.

- **Monitoring Temperature Technology Based**

The temperature of the people were assisted with the help of wireless thermometer at entry and exit points of gates of society, office, hotels, railways, banks, airports, shops, malls, and all public places.

- **Work From Home**

The "WORK FROM HOME" is the new normal in all the parts of the world due to this pandemic situation. As high as 88% of the workforce prefer to "WORK FROM HOME" and 69% believe that their productivity has increased because of working remotely at home with flexibility and the comfort zone of their home. With this new technologies

and innovations and the digitalisation trend and the work from new normal will have a positive impact on our economy and will also lead to sustainable development.

- **Various Activities And Services With The Help Of Technology**

In this hard times difficult times with full of crises and COVID-19 Pandemic, technology proved a boon to us in carrying out ICT enabled learning, Electronic Banking, Digital Business, Electronic Payments also knowns as Cashless Payments, Electronic Commerce the global trend, Work from home a flexible solution, online Entertainment via various digital platforms, applications developed specially for tracing the spread of this infectious communicable respiratory disease, share market, contactless delivery, robotics for various services, applications for staying fit at home, learning cooking, education, to monitor the temperatures with the help of temperature etc.

Conclusion:

The whole world fights against the corona virus disease which is an infectious respiratory disease also knowns as COVID-19 which has been declared as a pandemic by the World Health Organization popularly known in short as WHO. Technology helps us a lot and makes the things speedier, faster, convenient, effective and more efficient and a brighter, smarter future. And thus in this hard times of COVID-19 Pandemic, technology proved a boon to us in carrying out ICT enabled learning, Electronic Banking, Digital Business, Electronic Payments also knowns as Cashless Payments, Electronic Commerce the global trend, Work from home a flexible solution, online Entertainment via various digital platforms, applications developed specially for tracing the spread of this infectious communicable respiratory disease, share market, contactless delivery in this hard times to control the spread of infection and avoid going out, robotics for various services, applications for staying fit at home, learning cooking, education, to monitor the temperatures with the help of wireless thermometers etc. thus, during this hard and difficult times of pandemic technology proved a boon. The innovations in technology proved a boon and helped us during this adversity of COVID-19 Pandemic and with more advancement in technology we are going to have a better, higher, brighter, smarter and a wiser future.

References

- T. J. (2001). Information technology, strategic decision making approaches and organizational performance in different industrial settings. *The Journal of Strategic Information Systems*, 10(2), 101-119. doi:10.1016/s0963-8687(01)00043-9
- Bakos, J. Y., & Brynjolfsson, E. (1993). Information Technology, Incentives, and the Optimal Number of Suppliers. *Journal of Management Information Systems*, 10(2), 37-53. doi:10.1080/07421222.1993.11517999
- Digital India Programme: Ministry of Electronics & Information Technology(MeitY) Government of India. (2020, November 23). Retrieved from <https://www.digitalindia.gov.in/>
- Digital India. (2021, January 05). Retrieved from https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Digital_India
- Mihalís Kritikós (2020) „Ten technologies to fight coronavirus“, European Parliamentary Research Service. available at:
[https://www.europal.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2020/641543/EPRS_IDA\(2020\)641543_EN.pdf](https://www.europal.europa.eu/RegData/etudes/IDAN/2020/641543/EPRS_IDA(2020)641543_EN.pdf)
- F. (2019, December 30). Digitalisation is driving India to a \$5-trillion economy. Retrieved from <https://www.financialexpress.com/industry/digitalisation-is-driving-india-to-a-5-trillion-economy/1806989/>
- PN, B. (2020, August 06). Role of Technology in the Era of COVID-19 Pandemic. Retrieved from <https://news.cleartax.in/role-of-technology-in-the-era-of-covid-19-pandemic/>

- S. J. Daniel, (2020) "Education and the COVID-19 pandemic," Prospects, no. 0123456789, 2020, doi: 10.1007/s11125-020-09464-3.
- Veena Shenoy, Sheetal Mahendher, N. V. (2020) (PDF) COVID 19 Lockdown Technology Adaption, Teaching, Learning, Students Engagement and Faculty Experience, Mukta Shabd Journal. Available at:
https://www.researchgate.net/publication/340609688_COVID_19_Lockdown_Technology_Adaption_Teaching_Learning_Students_Engagement_and_Faculty_Experience (Accessed: 23 July 2020).